

FORMATION OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES FOREIGN EXPERIENCES AND POSSIBILITIES OF THEIR APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Aliyeva Musaffo G'ayrat qizi

Karshi institute of engineering economics
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ABSTRACT

This article presents concepts and theoretical analyzes of the management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises. In addition, the relevance of conceptual, theoretical and practical researches and innovative processes, views on the management of scientific and technical development depends on many reasons.

There are several general similarities in the government mechanisms for the economic growth of regional industries in developed countries. However, countries also have national characteristics, which are characterized by the level of economic growth and the presence of problems of regional growth. Mechanisms for comprehensive development of industrial economic growth in the regions appeared in Europe in the 1950s, in America in the 1960s, and in Asia in the 1970s.

We can see that the industrial gas and basic chemical production in China has a business growth of 2.2 percent in 2022. And we can see that 2017-2022 China's industrial gas and basic chemical production business will grow by 2.3% annually. China's industrial gas and basic chemical industry has grown strongly over the past five years to 2022. Industry revenue is expected to grow at an annual rate of \$5.7 billion over the five years through 2022, to \$94.1 billion. Economic growth in China and demand for stable downstream industries in steel, petrochemical, metallurgy and general chemical industries mainly drove industrial development during this period. The figures for industrial gas and basic chemical production in China from 2012 to 2022 were as follows.

Another industry that is very well developed in China is the automobile industry. Therefore, in the development of industrial structures, there should be significant capital, that is, the volume of work in industrial enterprises depends more on the total capital. In China's passenger car manufacturing industry, the highest business expenses as a share of revenue are wages (4.3%), procurement (66.4%), and rent and utilities (1.6%). The Chinese government is actively encouraging domestic car manufacturers to develop environmentally friendly and fuel-efficient cars as a strategic mission to take the lead in the global automotive industry. To date, the Chinese auto industry has already mastered the production of cars that

meet the Euro-5 standard. Therefore, in the implementation of these processes, a number of production enterprises will be necessary, so in the following picture, we can analyze the automobile manufacturing enterprises by year.

The dynamics of the gross domestic product in 2018-2020 of the countries that are currently among the developed countries, as well as the economic growth rates of the year under consideration, are shown.

Indicators of industrial production in the Russian Federation show a positive growth trend during the study period. Thus, in 2020, this indicator was 606.69 billion US dollars, in contrast to 556.4 in the corresponding period of 2014. had organized The index of industrial production describes the change in the production process and classifies economic activity with a set of goods, divided into the following types:

- Mining,
- Electricity production
- Gas production
- Water distribution.

1- table. Indicators of industrial development index by country from 2011 to 2020 are presented.

Table 1.

Indicators of industrial development index by country from 2013 to 2022 (in percentage terms)

Country	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Azerbaijan	100	95.0	92.8	94.5	93.8	96.1	95.6	92.4	93.4	95.0
Germany	100	107.1	106.2	106.1	107.5	109.0	110.5	113.5	114.6	109.5
Israel	100	102.1	106.2	106.7	108.0	110.4	112.2	116.3	120.4	123.4
Italy	100	100.4	94.4	91.5	90.5	92.1	93.4	96.2	97.6	96.6
Kyrgyzstan	100	111.9	94.1	121.0	119.1	113.8	119.4	133.2	140.4	150.0
Lithuania	100	106.6	110.9	114.2	114.5	119.5	122.8	131.4	137.8	142.4
Poland	100	106.7	108.0	110.6	114.4	119.9	123.3	131.4	139.2	145.0
Russia	100	105.0	108.5	110.5	113.2	114.8	116.3	117.2	120.6	123.7
England	100	100.0	97.6	96.6	98.1	99.1	100.3	102.3	102.7	101.7
USA	100	103.1	106.1	108.2	111.6	110.8	109.4	106.5	103.8	114.2
Uzbekistan	100	106.5	114.8	125.7	136.2	146.9	156.0	168.5	98.6	85.7
Ukraine	100	108.0	107.2	102.6	92.2	80.2	82.5	82.9	84.2	82.7
France	100	102.6	99.9	99.0	97.9	99.6	100.3	102.4	103.1	103.2

Based on the data presented in Table 1, it can be seen that the index of industrial production (taken as 100 in 2013) for each considered country has an uncertain trend of growth and decline. As can be seen from the list of countries under consideration, the studied indicator in 2022 compared to 2013 has a negative downward trend in the following countries: Azerbaijan, Italy and Ukraine. It should also be noted that the following countries have the largest growth in the index of industrial development during the period under study:

Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Poland, Republic of Moldova and Uzbekistan. It shows a positive trend in the industrial development of the countries and contributes to it.

The ideas of a scientific approach, which are characteristic of the management and security of the industrial structure, were presented by foreign economists Taylor, Frank, We can see that it has been adequately developed by Lilian Gilbreth and Henry Gantt. As the creators of industrial management, they were highly effective in perfecting many manual operations by using observation, measurement, logic, and analysis.

In his scientific works, the foreign scientist U. Taylor recognized that the main principles of the idea of "management" are as follows:

- the most convenient methods of production developing, based on the development of learning such as the time, effort, focus or effort spent on it;
- absolute compliance with developed standards to get
- workers to their jobs and assignments must be selected, trained and placed so that they will show the highest results;
- pay wages according to work results;
- use of their tasks of managers who carry out control in a special specialized direction;
- creating and maintaining a friendly relationship between workers and managers in order to ensure the possibility of management.

Economic and information security of industrial enterprises and their protection methods from foreign scientists V.K. Senchagov, from the point of view, the economic security of the enterprise includes a combination of these factors, does not depend only on the internal situation, the impact of external factors of the enterprise and the enterprise's response to economic threats defines it as a set of measures.

A.H. Glumov and YE.P. Kiselitsiy stated that the economic security of the enterprise is the qualitative and quantitative level of economic security characterized by the sum of indicators, the main of which is determined by evaluating the state of use of the enterprise's resources according to the economic security criteria. gave

If we divide the industry of the region economically into groups, it is mainly composed of the following natural resources;

1. Natural resources of general importance;
2. Material production resources;
3. Service sector resources,

For many of the most modern economic theories, "post-industrial society", "information society", "knowledge economy", "industrial institutional structure" D. Bell, Considered in the works of E. Toffler, K. Drogobitskaya and a number of other scientists. However, some terminological restrictions do not always reflect the essence of the views.

In the Republic of Korea, the law "On Comprehensive National Planning of Regional Development" was adopted and special parks were established within the networks. Much attention is paid to the development of infrastructures. Programs for the development of technoparks and technopolises have been developed. In developing countries, especially in Turkey, state support and encouragement of regions is high, with special attention paid to the establishment of growth points. A number of regional programs and investment projects have been developed and are being implemented in the country.

As a result of the development of integration processes in Europe, the role of regional

policy within the European Economic Community has been steadily increasing in recent years. Ten years ago, it was considered an additional direction of the EU's activity, necessary only to achieve progress in strategically important areas. By the end of the 80s, it gained serious independent importance. Now, in connection with the entry into force of the Maastricht Treaty on the establishment of the European Union, not only the possibility of implementing the regional policy of the EU has significantly expanded, but also the role of individual regions of the countries considered to be members of the Union has increased within the integration process. Within the framework of the EU, regional policy is implemented based on the following principles:

- concentration of structural fund resources in the least developed regions of the EU, with strict control over dispersal of funds. 80% of the financial payments made from this fund should be given to regions that are lagging behind in economic development;
- structural subsidies have a complementary nature, that is, EU institutions can provide resources as an additional resource only during the implementation of national programs, and on their own initiative, their own intervention do not have the right to define their objects;
- Macroeconomic and political harmonization of EU regional policy of each member country of the group. By providing financial support to national programs of regional development, the EU authorities should ensure that the integration directions do not conflict with the tasks of the economic policy of this country, and that the funds allocated from the EU budget are not squandered due to the lack of mutual consultation between national and local authorities;
- Implementation of national regional programs by EU countries based on direct cooperation between them. In particular, it concerns the exchange of information between the respective governments in order to ensure the clarity of the objectives and methods of implementation of national programs.

The researches of influential international organizations and scientists have justified regional tourism as the direction with the most stable growth potential in the future. Therefore, tourism serves as a leading sector and a point of growth in the sustainable development of regions. The reforms implemented in Uzbekistan are aimed at strengthening economic relations with the world community, including the tourism sector.

China's experience is based on the concept of "Using the relative competitive advantages of the regions", while implementing the concept of "Allocation of production forces on the basis of mutual equality". Priority is given to regions with the highest potential for the organization of production of competitive products (services) and development of tourism. Along with the development of the "Open Zones" system, attention is paid to other central cities and districts of the country for the establishment of special economic zones.

The world experience of regional policy is characterized by the presence of the following general trends: decentralization, interregional integration, environmental protection, population welfare, etc.

At present, Uzbekistan has not developed a general strategy for regional development and specific mechanisms of promotion. Subsidies and grants to certain regions within the framework of the state budget can be shown as a mechanism. Also, medium-term development forecasts of regions, social and economic development state programs for some regions (networks) have been developed, and incentives for regions in terms of attracting and

encouraging foreign investments, developing small and private business (in the field of tourism) and there are government decisions to provide facilities.

In the implementation of regional policy in many countries, the mechanisms of development of target programs, support of border regions, establishment of special economic zones and clusters are widely used.

Relative evaluation of the use of mechanisms of state regulation of the development of regions in Uzbekistan and foreign countries is widely covered in AM Sodikov's monograph entitled "Basics of Regional Development: Theory, Methodology, Practice" Table 2.

Table 2

Comparative analysis of the use of levers of state regulation of regions in Uzbekistan and foreign countries

Mechanisms for regulating the development of regions	Foreign countries	in Uzbekistan
adoption of laws and normative documents for the development of regions	A2	B
Operation of state management bodies regulating the development of regions	A2	B
Regional development programming and indicative planning	A2	B
Establishment of development of green corridors, free economic zones, industrial parks and zones	A2	B
Organization of production infrastructures in countries at the expense of the state: roads and railways, irrigation systems, pipelines, etc.	A1	A2
Organization of social infrastructure facilities in the regions at the expense of the state	A1	A2
Regulation of placement of industrial enterprises and agricultural crops	A1	A2
Limitation of industrial development in developed districts by means of administrative methods	A2	B
Encouragement of companies importing production	A1	B
State reimbursement of construction costs of new industrial enterprises	A1	A2
Subsidizing regional and local budgets	A2	A2
Incentive measures aimed at attracting private capital to troubled areas	A2	B
Providing various benefits to foreign investors	A1	A1
Provision of preferential loans and tax incentives for locating enterprises in priority areas	A2	A1

Conditional marks 1) A2 - wide, in many countries; 2) A1 - partially, in some countries; 3) B - not applicable.

The growth points aimed at supporting and stimulating regional development, which are widely used abroad, are not used enough in Uzbekistan to establish special economic zones and attract private capital to

regions. These measures, the development of infrastructure objects (motorways and railways, information technologies and communication systems, special warehouses, etc.) are of decisive importance in increasing the competitiveness of the country's regions.

Summary. Foreign experiences of forming the management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises and the possibilities of their application in Uzbekistan are important. With the goal of economic growth and development of the industrial sector of Uzbekistan, the use of foreign experiences is important to increase its innovative and new technology development processes. Important parts of foreign experiences and sharing opportunities in Uzbekistan can be summarized as follows. Bringing foreign experiences and applying them in Uzbekistan is important for increasing the country's economic development. It will be an important tool for learning new technologies, improving product quality, and improving innovative development processes. The state, enterprises and the academic field should create opportunities to attract, use and apply their experiences to the economic growth of Uzbekistan.

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